

INFLUENCE OF TEXTILE DIELECTRIC MATERIALS ON SPIRAL-TYPE FSS FOR 5G APPLICATIONS

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Resume - With the advance of wireless communication technologies, there is a need for innovative solutions for frequency spectrum management. This work proposes the design of Frequency Selective Surfaces (FSS) with a geometry inspired by the Ulam Spiral, using some textile materials, with the aim of optimizing signal filtering in the 3.5 GHz band for communication applications.

Keywords: FSS; Ulam Spiral; Filter, 5G, Textile materials.

INTRODUCTION

Frequency Selective Surfaces (FSS) are structures designed to act as spatial filters, widely applied in telecommunications, such as Wi-Fi networks. These structures consist of periodic arrangements, that can be configured in 2D or 3D arrays, composed of identical elements arranged on one or more sides of a dielectric layer. The elements of the unit cell can be of metallic conductive patch type, aperture or fully dielectric materials [1].

FSS can exhibit different filtering behaviors according to their frequency response. When made up of openings, they act as band-pass filters, allowing signals to pass through in certain frequency bands. When made up of conductive elements, they act as band-reject filters, blocking signals at certain frequencies [2]. Some FSS can combine blocking and transmission functions in a single structure, offering multiband responses, tailored according to the type and geometry of the elements in the unit cell.

The literature on FSS explores various element geometries, with emphasis on rectangular and circular models [3]. In this study, the Ulam Spiral was selected as the basis for the analysis. The article proposes a compact FSS with a geometry based on this spiral, presenting a response range between 3.2 GHz and 4 GHz, suitable for use in communication technologies like 5G.

DEVELOPMENT

The Ulam Spiral, also called the Cousins' Spiral, is an intriguing numerical pattern discovered by mathematician Stanislaw Ulam in 1963 during a lecture. While doodling, Ulam identified this remarkable mathematical structure, which has since come to be known by its name [4]. This pattern organizes the natural numbers in a spiral sequence starting from the number 1, with each number represented by a square [5].

By arranging the positive integers in a counterclockwise spiral arrangement, Ulam observed that the prime numbers tended to cluster along the diagonals, as shown in Fig. 1. This grouping highlights a peculiar distribution of prime numbers, providing a fascinating visual representation of their organization.

100	99	98	97	96	95	94	93	92	91
65	64	63	62	61	60	59	58	57	90
66	87	36	35	34	33	32	31	56	89
67	38	17	16	15	14	13	30	55	88
68	39	18	5	4	3	12	29	54	87
69	40	19	6	1	2	11	28	53	86
70	41	20	7	8	9	10	27	52	85
71	42	21	23	24	25	26	51	84	
72	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	83
73	74	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82

Figure 1. Ulam's spiral with the first 100 values [5]

There are several ways to modify the original Ulam's Spiral by changing the parameters that define it. These variations may involve adjusting the initial value of the spiral, changing the direction from counterclockwise to clockwise and experimenting with different geometric shapes, such as heptagons, other polygons, or even circular shapes [5].

The geometry proposed for the computationally designed FSS structure is inspired by the Ulam Spiral, following the approach presented in [6], where the authors also incorporated the Ulam Spiral into their design. In this configuration, squares with a side length of 1.54 mm are removed at positions corresponding to prime numbers. The overall geometry is derived from a square patch with dimensions of 16.94 mm by 16.94 mm, as depicted in Fig. 2.

Three types of textile materials were used, each with specific configurations, as shown in Table 1. The materials selected include *cotton plain*, *jeans*, *elano wool plain*, *elano wool twill*, *polyester plain 0.36*, *wool*, *viscose+pe* and *wool+pa* [7]. Each material was chosen for its unique properties, enabling a complete analysis and resulting in meaningful results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The method used to simulate the structure was the Method of Moments (MOM), whose results can be seen in Fig.

Figure 2. Geometry of the proposed FSS. []

Figure 4. Simulated results obtained in terms of transmission.

Table 1. Used textile materials.

Materials	Weave	ϵ_r	$\text{tg}(\delta)$	Thickness
Cotton	plain	2.007	0.0314	0.48
Jeans	-	1.9	0.008	0.6
Elano Wool	plain	1.67	0.0073	1.26
Elano Wool	twill	2.053	0.0076	0.64
Polyester	plain	1.748	0.0044	0.36
Wool	plain	1.865	0.0079	0.42
Viscose + PE	twill	2.2	0.0009	0.52
Wool + PA	twill	1.529	0.0052	1.47

Figure 3. Simulated results obtained in terms of transmission.

res 3 and 4. Initially, it can be seen that the filter bands obtained for the materials *cotton plain*, *jeans*, *elano wool plain*, *elano wool twill*, *polyester plain 0.36*, *wool*, *viscose+pe* and *wool+pa* are 420 MHz, 440 MHz, 440 MHz, 420 MHz, 420 MHz, 420 MHz, 440 MHz and 440 MHz, respectively. In addition, the resonance frequencies for these materials occur at 3.54 GHz, 3.52 GHz, 3.52 GHz, 3.68 GHz, 3.62 GHz, 3.64 GHz and 3.58 GHz, in that order.

Based on the results shown in Figures 3 e 4, it can be concluded that the proposed FSS is capable of filtering the 5G application band at 3.5 GHz. In Brazil, devices using this technology operate in the frequency range between 3.3 GHz and 3.7 GHz, according to [8]. In the US, the band used is between 3.45 GHz and 3.98 GHz. In Europe, the 3.4-3.8 GHz band is used for 5G, while the 3.8-4.2 GHz band is under study. In Japan, the 3.4-4.1 GHz band is used for both 4G and 5G, and in the countries of the Arab League, the 3.3-3.8 GHz band is agreed, with Saudi Arabia in particular intending to designate the 3.3-4.2 GHz band for public and private mobile networks [9]. The filtering of this band is illustrated in Figure. It is worth noting that in this figure, an insertion loss of -10 dB was adopted as the Reference Level (RL) for filtering.

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